

The effect of working on vocabulary in English classes

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Abstract: this article provides feedback on the effectiveness of working on dictionaries in English language classes in general secondary schools, and important tools that should be implemented in this regard.

Key words: vocabulary, communication culture, fluency, free thinking, results, speech.

Increasing vocabulary in learning English is one of the important components of language acquisition. Although knowing the grammar rules of the language is important, expanding the vocabulary increases the student's ability to communicate, understand texts and express ideas. This article also talks about the importance of the process of working with dictionaries, methods and ways to ensure effective results. It is worth noting that working on dictionaries plays an important role in the development of language skills of many students.

Working with dictionaries offers the following advantages:

1. Fluency of communication - Vocabulary allows students to use language freely and effectively. They will be able to use more words and phrases to express themselves on different topics.
2. Develop text comprehension – Knowing the meanings of words makes it easier for students to understand texts. Students who learn new vocabulary read more complex texts and understand their content more clearly.
3. Improving language skills - Expanding vocabulary has a positive effect on all language skills - listening, speaking, reading and writing. Students who have mastered vocabulary express correct and effective ideas in written and oral communication.
4. **Development of social skills** - Students with good vocabulary can communicate successfully with different cultures and people. This will help them to be more active in social life. Different methods and techniques are used in English lessons to effectively work on vocabulary. These methods help students learn words easily and effectively. For

example, learning through context, that is, when learning new vocabulary, it is very important to know the context in which the word is used. It is easier for students to understand the meaning of words through texts, sentences or situations. With this method, students understand the exact meaning of a word and how it is used in different situations. In addition, the method of introducing new words and repeating them is very effective in learning vocabulary.

The teacher repeats the new words several times, teaches their pronunciation and together with the students shows the use of the words in different contexts. This method helps to remember new vocabulary faster. Especially, by dividing students into pairs and working with dictionaries together, their interaction will increase. Each pair explains the newly learned words to each other and makes small dialogues or conversations using the learned vocabulary. This process makes the words more effective in practice. Learning new words through audio materials is very beneficial for students. By listening, students learn how to pronounce words and understand how they are used in real-life situations. This method makes it possible to simultaneously develop listening and speaking skills while learning vocabulary.

Vocabulary Learning Strategies There are some strategies that can be used to make vocabulary learning more effective. These strategies help students learn words faster and more effectively:

1. Associative learning. By making associations when learning new vocabulary, students remember words better. For example, new words can be associated with familiar concepts or images. This method helps to store words in long-term memory.
2. Working with groups of words. It is more effective for students to study vocabulary in groups. For example, words related to plants, animals, food, or home furnishings can be divided into separate groups. This method allows students to learn words on the same topic faster.
3. Generalization of concepts. Combining words based on common concepts and learning together is also one of the effective methods. For example, students expand their

vocabulary by identifying similarities between words in the same group, finding their synonyms and antonyms.

4. Visual approach. Learning new vocabulary through pictures, graphs, and diagrams is effective for most students. Visual aids help to better understand the meaning of words and to remember them faster.

There are also ways to strengthen vocabulary in English. In the process of learning new vocabulary, it is very important to constantly strengthen them. The following methods can be used for this:

1. Tests and surveys. Students should be allowed to recall and reinforce the vocabulary they have learned through regular tests and quizzes. This method encourages students to constantly review new vocabulary.

2. Written exercises. Using new vocabulary through written exercises will help students master these words better. For example, students can write texts or compose essays based on newly learned words. This method helps them learn how to use different forms of words.

3. Conversations and dialogues. Students can practice and reinforce the vocabulary they have learned through conversations and dialogues. Teachers should create situations that allow them to use newly learned words when choosing topics of conversation in lessons.

4. Mobile applications and online resources. Nowadays, various mobile applications and online platforms make vocabulary learning more convenient and effective. For example, applications such as Quizlet, Memrise, and Anki allow students to learn words using various games, tests, and flashcards. Also, these platforms encourage students to repeat words continuously and help them to use advanced approaches. This makes learning vocabulary not only effective, but also interesting.

Assessing Vocabulary Learning
Continuous assessment of vocabulary learning is essential to monitor students' progress. The following methods may be used in the evaluation process:

1. Dictation and listening exercises. Dictation helps students assess how well they use newly learned words in writing. It is also possible to see what results students have achieved in hearing words and understanding their pronunciation through listening exercises.

2. Pronunciation check. It is also important to observe that students are using the newly learned vocabulary correctly in their pronunciation. By pronouncing new words correctly, they become more fluent and intelligible.

3. Tests. Assessment of newly learned vocabulary through tests is an important tool in determining the level of student memory of words. In tests, it is determined how deeply students understand the meaning of words by choosing synonyms, antonyms or correct sentences.

4. Practical exercises. The level of students' application of newly learned words in everyday life should also be evaluated. Observing their ability to use the new vocabulary correctly and fluently in their conversations or writing shows how well they have mastered the words they have learned.

In conclusion, working on dictionaries in English language classes is important for the development of students' language skills. Learning new vocabulary improves students' communication skills, understanding texts, and expanding their opportunities to express themselves. It is important to use a variety of methods and strategies, as well as regular assessment and revision, to make the vocabulary work process effective. Teachers should encourage and continuously support students to learn vocabulary in fun and effective ways. Thus, expanding the vocabulary is the main factor in improving students' ability to communicate freely and fluently in English.

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